

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 133:0 A Song of Ascents, of David.</p> <p>Psa. 133:1 Behold, how good and how pleasant it is For ^abrothers to dwell together in unity! ² It is like the precious ^aoil upon the head, Coming down upon the beard, <i>Even</i> Aaron's beard, Coming down upon the ^bedge of his robes. ³ It is like the ^adew of ^bHermon Coming down upon the ^cmountains of Zion; For there the LORD ^dcommanded the blessing — ^elife forever.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 133:1 שִׁיר הַמַּעֲלוֹת לְדָוִד הַנְּהַיָּה</p> <p>מֵה־טוֹב וּמֵה־נְעִים שְׁבֵת אֶחָיִם גַּם־יִחָדָּר : ² כַּשֶּׁמֶן הַטוֹב אֶעֱלֶה־ הָרֹאשׁ יִרְדַּעַל־הַיֶּקֶן זֶקֶן־אֶהְרֹן שִׁירְדַּעַל־פִּי מִדֹּתָיו : ³ כְּטֹל־ תְּרִמֹן שִׁירְדַּעַל־הַרְרֵי צִיּוֹן כִּי שָׁם אֶצְוֶה יְהוָה אֶת־הַבְּרָכָה תְּלִים עַד־ הָעוֹלָם :</p>

References

Psalm 133:1

^aGen 13:8; Heb 13:1

Psalm 133:2

^aEx 29:7; 30:25, 30; Lev 8:12

^bEx 28:33; 39:24

Psalm 133:3

^aProv 19:12; Hos 14:5; Mic 5:7

^bDeut 3:9; 4:48

^cPs 48:2; 74:2; 78:68

^dLev 25:21; Deut 28:8; Ps 42:8

^ePs 21:4

Targum

Psa. 133:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss. Behold, how good and how pleasant is the dwelling of Zion and Jerusalem, together indeed like two brothers. ² Like the fine oil that is poured on the head, coming down on the beard, the beard of Aaron, that comes down to the hem of his garments. ³ Like the dew of Hermon that comes down on the mountains of Zion; for there the LORD has commanded the blessing, life forevermore.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

David inherited from Saul a war-torn country. There was a civil war that occurred after Saul's death. Saul had other sons besides Jonathan who claimed the throne. David gathered his men and defeated Saul's remaining sons. David spent a lot of energy to bring the country together. It was Solomon who completed this task. In this Psalm, it is Moses and Aaron who provided the quintessential example of fraternal love. The two brothers were very different in their nature and action. However, they complimented each other and provided the leadership needed for Israel when they left Egypt.

Notes on this Psalm

The psalmist wants people to realize that unity is better than disunity. When a people are unified, they will produce and do wondrous things. When the people are ready to damage each other, that is all they think about. It is also important to accept that people are different. Moses and Aaron were completely different men. However, their differences complimented each other. That is a lesson people need to learn today. The Torah says that a house divided will not stand.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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